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Effect of Different Mulching Practices on Weeds and Yield Attributes of Cotton Variety Sindh-1

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Abstract

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is a major fiber crop of Pakistan. Weeds are undesirable plants which impact growth and yield of cotton. Weeds can be decreased by applying various types of mulching, water extracts of allelopathic plants, including sorghum, sunflower and herbicide treatment. The present investigation was designed to assess the effect of different mulching practices on weeds and yield attributes of cotton variety Sindh-1 was conducted at Cotton Research Institute, Agriculture Research Centre, Tando Jam, during the year 2017, throughout Kharif season, 2017, in triplicate with a (RCBD) with net plot size of 4m x 3m (12m²). The experiment comprised cotton variety Sindh-1 and two mulching materials such as wheat chaff and banana leaves, each applied at 12 t ha⁻¹ and a check without mulching treatment. Our study disclosed that the maximum plant height (128.63 cm), sympodial branches plant⁻¹ (19.63), opened bolls plant⁻¹ (46.98), weight of seed cotton (2.60), weight of seed cotton plant⁻¹ (112.46 g), seed index (8.72 g), seed cotton yield (5300 kg ha⁻¹), staple length (29.00 mm), ginning out-turn ratio (33.59%) and oil content (22.49%) were noted in banana leaves as mulching material. The same treatment produced the maximum leaf area (134.60 cm²), and leaf area index (4.40 cm). The minimum weed density (55.67 m⁻²), weed fresh (293.80 g m⁻²) and dry biomass (134.30 g m⁻²) with maximum weed control (77.84%) was recorded with banana leaves as mulching material in Sindh-1. It is determined that mulching with banana leaves (12 tons ha⁻¹) considerably increased agronomic and physiological characters of cotton variety Sindh-1 and reduced the weeds, as compared to mulching material of wheat straw @ 12 t. ha⁻¹ and control (untreated). Thus, it is suggested that mulching with banana leaves must be added in weed management strategy of cotton.

Keywords: Cotton; Fiber; Seed Yield; Straw; Mulching

1. Introduction:

Pakistan ranks 5th among cotton producing countries worldwide. Cotton crop contributes major share in foreign exchange of the country. In Pakistan, cotton is the 2nd largest cultivated crops after wheat, which produces 4.1% share in agriculture and 0.8% for

national gross domestic product (Pakistan Economic Survey, 2019-20). Cotton is typically used for fiber purpose; however, the cotton seed oil plays an important role in the national oil industry by contributing about 66% share in domestic vegetable

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oil production (Shuli *et al.*, 2018).

Cotton production in Pakistan is relatively low as equalled to further countries in the world. There are so many factors those interfere with the cotton crop's low yield, but weeds have significantly affected cotton crop (Dogan *et al.*, 2014). Thus, weed infestation is a major factor in the poor cotton yield (Zhang *et al.*, 2014). Cotton fields are infested with different species of weeds like sedges, grasses, broad leaves. The weeds reduce cotton production and affect lint quality. The time of initial growth and wide spacing favours rapid growth of weeds in cotton fields (Singh & Kokate, 2010). The negative effects of weed on yield and its quality of cotton are distinct. Weeds absorb more water as compared to cotton plants, eventually, the yield decreased significantly. The seeds free from weeds, irrigation water also helpful for controlling weeds in cotton crop cultivation (Xiao *et al.*, 2015) and whereas manual weed management practices are difficult. The weeds participate with light, nutrients, moisture, affect flower roots by means of liberating the minor materials into the rhizosphere (Nadeem *et al.*, 2013). Weeds can be managed by various control techniques i.e., mechanical control, biological control, cultural and chemical controls (Prabhu *et al.*, 2012). Allelopathy offers great potential to resolve the weeds in crops (Hozayn *et al.*, 2011a). The allelopathy could be implemented for weed management in cotton. The allelopathic crop, sorghum, sunflower use in cotton help to control the weeds, recover cotton plants, increasing lint yield and economic benefit (Khaliq *et al.*, 2011). The allelochemicals mostly secreted during secondary metabolism by plants which are by-products of primary metabolic processes as seed, stem, roots of living and decomposing of plants material and consequently influence on weed density and its growth (Batish *et al.*, 2001; Tesio and Ferrero, 2010). Allelochemicals release from many plants, leaves, stems, roots and fruits and seeds, interfere with growth and development of other plants (Asgharipour, 2011). The allelopathic crops are also used for mulching purposes for controlling the weeds.

1.1. Objectives:

- To assess the effect of different mulching practices on weeds and yield attributes of cotton variety Sindh-1.

2. Materials and Methods:

2.1. Study Area:

A field study was conducted at the student's experimental farm of the Department of Agronomy, Sindh Agriculture University, Tandojam during 2017,

located at 25°25'60" N and 68°31'60" E. High temperature ranges cool to cold in season and hot to very hot throughout summer. During the study period, relative humidity ranged between 37.88 to 73.28%. More rainfall 17.58 and 4.05 mm was observed during the 1st and 4th weeks of August 2017. Before the conduction of the experiment, pre-soil analysis (0-30 cm) regarding various physicochemical properties was done using standard procedures (Klute, 1986; Sparks *et al.*, 1996). The soil of experimental area was clay soil in texture, non-saline, low in biological substance (0.72-0.88%), low in available phosphorus (3.90-4.94 and mg kg⁻¹) but high in exchangeable potassium (84.58-112.18 mg kg⁻¹).

2.2. Experimental Design and Treatments:

The cotton variety Sindh-1 was selected against two mulching materials of wheat straw and banana leaves (Figure 2). The treatments have been set up in a three-part randomized complete block design (RCBD). In each plot, there was control without any mulch treatment. The net plot size in each replicate was 4 x 3 m². The mulching materials (wheat straw and banana leaves) collected from the field and applied between the rows at the rate of 12 t ha⁻¹ (Ashrafi *et al.*, 2008).

2.3. Cultural Practices:

The field was irrigated before seedbed preparation. After, getting a workable moisture regime, the seedbed was prepared with two ploughings followed by planking. Delinted and fumigated cotton seeds (15 kg ha⁻¹) were sown using a manual seed drill and a distance of 75 and 30 cm between row after row and plant after plant respectively was continued. Recommended agronomic practices were followed. For fertilizer application, the recommended dose of phosphorus (90 kg ha⁻¹) using di-ammonium phosphate (DAP) was applied during preparation of seedbed while half of the recommended nitrogen (120 kg ha⁻¹) using urea was useful at the time of sowing. The other half was useful 30 days after sowing. The field was irrigated as per the requirement of the crop. Six irrigations were applied in total during the whole period for the experiment. The initial picking was carried out when the 50% of the bolls had opened. While the consequent second and third takings were approved out when the majority of the bolls were opened.

2.4. Growth, Yield and Physiological Parameters:

The data regarding various agronomic and physiological parameters of cotton and weed control

parameters were recorded. For plant height, five plants after separately plot were randomly particular, and measuring tape was used. Sympodial branches bearing direct buds and fruits were counted from the five plants from individually plot and the mean was calculated. The quantity of opened and un-opened bolls plant⁻¹ was done by counting all opened bolls from five plants from each plot and means were calculated. For the mass of seed cotton boll⁻¹ (g), seed cotton of 20 bolls from each plot was picked, weighed, and then seed cotton boll⁻¹ was calculated. Similarly, seed cotton from five plants was collected from each treatment and weighed by electronic weight balance, and the mean was calculated for the weight of seed cotton per plant (g). Similarly, seed cotton yield plot⁻¹ (kg) and then per hectare was calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Seed cotton yield} = \frac{\text{Yield plot}^{-1}}{\text{Area of plot (m}^2)} \times 1000$$

After separating the seeds from seed cotton by the ginning process, 100 seeds were occupied randomly from each plot and evaluated by electronic weight balance (g) for the calculation of seed index. Lint yield was calculated by multiplying seed cotton yield with ginning out-turn (GOT) percentage. For GOT (%), seed cotton randomly taken from one square meter from each plot was ginned by an electronic ginner and the weight of lint and seed was weighed separately. The GOT (%) was calculated by the following formula:

$$\text{GOT (\%)} = \frac{\text{Lint yield}}{\text{Seed cotton yield}} \times 100$$

After ginning, a small quantity of lint randomly selected from five plants in each treatment was used for staple length (mm) measurement. For oil contents, ten cottonseeds were selected randomly from each treatment and weighed. The oil was extracted through the Soxhlet apparatus following AOAC (1990). A leaf area meter (LI- 3100C area meter) was used to determine the leaf area of five randomly chosen plants from each plot. The equation below was used to determine the leaf area index:

$$\text{Leaf area index (\%)} = \frac{\text{Leaf area cm}^{-1}}{\text{Ground area}} \times 100$$

2.5. Weed Control Parameters:

The different weeds species of cotton were observed and their frequency from each plot was recorded randomly to calculate weeds density using

the following formula:

$$\text{Weed density (m}^{-2}) = \frac{\text{Total no. of weeds for a given treatment}}{\text{Area (m}^{-2})}$$

Weed fresh weight (g m⁻²) was recorded by removing weeds from each plot and immediately weighed. For dry weight, weeds were put into a drying oven at 70 °C for 48 hours or until a constant weight was observed. For weed control (%) under different mulch treatments, the number of weeds in one square meter of each plot was counted and compared with control without any mulch treatment.

2.6. Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Statistix ver. 8.1. The difference between treatment means was compared using the least significant difference (LSD) test at p ≤ 0.05.

3. Results:

3.1. Influence of PH:

3.1.1. Plant height (cm) and Sympodial branches plant⁻¹:

It is evident from the analysis of variance that effect of mulching practices had highly significant (P>0.05) effect on plant height (cm), sympodial branches plant⁻¹, opened bolls plant⁻¹ and unopened bolls plant⁻¹ of cotton variety Sindh-1. It is revealed from the data presented in (Table 1) that mulching with banana leaves@12 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum plant height (128.63 cm), sympodial branches plant⁻¹ (19.60) as compared to wheat straw mulch@12 t ha⁻¹ which produced plant height (119.93cm), sympodial branches plant⁻¹ (16.46). However, reduction in plant height (80.90cm), sympodial branches plant⁻¹ (11.60) was noted in control (weedy check) plots.

3.1.2. Opened bolls plant⁻¹ and unopened bolls plant⁻¹:

Results demonstrated that shielding with banana leaves@12 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum opened boll plant⁻¹ (46.98) as compared to wheat straw mulch@12 t ha⁻¹ which produced opened bolls plant⁻¹ (39.04). However, decreased quantity of opened bolls plant⁻¹ (28.40) was calculate in control (weedy check) plots. The results further indicated that the maximum unopened bolls plant⁻¹ (7.16) was recorded in control (weedy check), followed by unopened bolls plant⁻¹ (5.30) was observed in wheat straw mulch @12 t ha⁻¹

and whereas the minimum unopened bolls plant⁻¹ @ 12 t ha⁻¹. (5.00) was examined in mulching with banana leaves

Table 1: Effect of mulching practices on agronomic traits of cotton variety Sindh-1

Treatments	Agronomic traits			
	Plant height(cm)	Sympodial branches plant ⁻¹	Opened bolls plant ⁻¹	Un opened bolls plant ⁻¹
Control (weedy check)	80.90 ^c	11.60 ^c	28.40 ^c	7.16 ^a
Mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	128.63 ^a	19.60 ^a	46.98 ^a	5.00 ^c
Mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	119.93 ^b	16.46 ^b	39.04 ^b	5.30 ^b
SE	0.49	0.15	0.12	0.22
LSD@0.05%	1.38	0.44	0.35	0.61

3.2. Yield Traits:

3.2.1. Weight of seed cotton boll⁻¹ and Weight of seed cotton plant⁻¹:

It is evident from the analysis of variance that effect of mulching practices had highly significant (P>0.05) effect on weight of seed cotton boll⁻¹ and mass of seed cotton plant⁻¹ of cotton variety Sindh-1. The data shown in (Table 2) revealed that covering with banana leaves@12 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum weight of seed cotton boll⁻¹ (2.60 g), weight of seed cotton plant⁻¹ (122.46 g) as compared to mulching with wheat straw@ 12 t ha⁻¹ which produced the weight of seed cotton boll⁻¹ (2.38 g) and weight of seed cotton plant⁻¹ (93.19 g). However, minimum weight of seed cotton boll⁻¹ (2.18 g), weight of seed cotton plant⁻¹ (61.62 g) was observed in control (weedy check).

3.2.2. Seed index (g) and Seed Cotton yield ha⁻¹:

The statistical analysis of variance displayed highly significant (P>0.05) variance in seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ of cotton variety Sindh-1 as affected by different mulching practices, whereas seed index (g) was significantly (P<0.05) affected by mulching practices. The data shown in (Table 2), revealed that covering with banana leaves@12 t ha⁻¹ recorded maximum weight of seed index (8.72 g) and seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ (5300 kg), as compared to mulching with wheat straw@ 12 t ha⁻¹ which produced the seed index (8.32 g) and seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ (4036 kg). Also supported our findings and reported that dry banana leaves could make a valuable contribution to soil fertility management and thereby improves the crop yield, reduced weeds. However, minimum seed index (7.93 g) and seed cotton yield ha⁻¹ (2666 kg) was observed in control (weedy check).

Table 2: Effect of mulching practices on yield traits of cotton variety Sindh-1

Treatments	Yield traits			
	Weight of seed cotton boll ⁻¹ (g)	Weight of seed cotton plant ⁻¹ (g)	Seed index weight (g)	Seed cotton Yield ha ⁻¹ (kg)
Control (weedy check)	2.18 ^c	61.62 ^c	7.93 ^c	2666 ^c
Mulching with banana leaves@ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	2.60 ^a	122.46 ^a	8.72 ^a	5300 ^a
Mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	2.38 ^b	93.19 ^b	8.32 ^b	4036 ^b
SE	0.01	0.79	0.05	33.98
LSD@0.05%	0.05	2.19	0.14	94.35

3.2. Qualitative Traits:

3.2.1. Staple length (mm), ginning out-turn (%) and oil content (%):

The statistical analysis of variance showed that mulching practices had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on staple length (mm) whereas mulching practices had highly significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on ginning outturn (%) and oil content (%) of cotton variety Sindh-1. The data presented in (Table 3) indicated that maximum staple length (29.00 mm), ginning outturn (33.59%)

and oil content (22.49%) recorded in banana leaves mulch @ 12 t ha⁻¹ as compared to wheat chaff mulch @ 12 t ha⁻¹ which produced the staple length (28.00 mm), ginning outturn (33.26%) and oil content (19.54%). However, minimum staple length (27.00 mm), ginning outturn (30.85%) and oil content (18.92%) was observed in control (weedy check).

Table 3: Effect of mulching practices on qualitative traits of cotton variety Sindh-1

Treatments	Qualitative traits		
	Staple length (mm)	Ginning out-turn (GOT %)	Oil content (%)
Control (weedy check)	27.00 ^c	30.85 ^c	18.92 ^c
Mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	29.00 ^a	33.59 ^a	22.49 ^a
Mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	28.00 ^b	33.26 ^b	19.54 ^b
SE	1.05	0.07	0.04
LSD @ 0.05%	2.92	0.21	0.12

3.4. Physiological Traits:

3.4.1. Leaf area (cm²), leaf area index (cm) and crop growth rate (gm² day⁻¹):

The statistical analysis of variance showed that mulching practices had significant effect ($P < 0.05$) on leaf area (cm²), leaf area index (cm) and crop growth rate (gm² day⁻¹) of cotton variety Sindh-1. The data presented in (Table 4) showed that the maximum leaf area (134.60 cm²) leaf area index (4.40 cm), crop

growth rate (5.87 gm² day⁻¹) was recorded in mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha⁻¹, followed by leaf area (124.58 cm²) leaf area index (4.32 cm), crop growth rate (5.53 gm² day⁻¹) observed in mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha⁻¹, whereas the lowest leaf area (96.80 cm²) leaf area index (2.72 cm), crop growth rate (4.27 gm² day⁻¹) were investigated in control (weedy check). The mean leaf area of the genotypes grew from 67.15 to 82.02 cm², while the mean under control conditions was 84.82 cm² and 62.59 cm² under water stress treatment conditions.

Table 4: Effect of mulching practices on physiological traits of cotton variety Sindh-1

Treatments	Physiological traits		
	Leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf area index (cm)	Crop growth rate (g m ² day ⁻¹)
Control (weedy check)	96.80 ^c	2.72 ^b	4.27 ^c
Mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	134.60 ^a	4.40 ^a	5.87 ^a
Mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	124.58 ^b	4.32 ^a	5.53 ^b
SE	0.10	0.03	0.03
LSD @ 0.05%	0.28	0.10	0.10

3.5. Weeds Traits:

3.5.1. Weed density (m⁻²) and weed fresh biomass (gm⁻²):

The statistical analysis of variance showed that mulching practices had highly significant ($P > 0.05$) effect on wild plant density (m⁻²), weed fresh biomass (gm⁻²). The data shown in (Table 5), revealed that

highest weed density (170.00 m⁻²), weed fresh biomass (875.60 gm⁻²) followed by weed density (64.33 m⁻²), fresh weed biomass (330.36 gm⁻²) was recorded in mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha⁻¹, whereas the smallest weed density (55.67 m⁻²), weed fresh biomass (293.80 gm⁻²) was observed in mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha⁻¹.

3.5.2. Weed Dry Biomass(gm^{-2}) and Weed Control (%):

The statistical analysis of variance showed that mulching practices had highly significant ($P>0.05$) effect on weed dry biomass (gm^{-2}) and weed control (%). The data shown in (Table 5), revealed that highest weed dry biomass ($406.20 gm^{-2}$) was found in weedy check (control), followed by weed dry biomass ($150.53 gm^{-2}$) was recorded in mulching with wheat straw@ 12 t ha⁻¹, whereas the minimum weed dry biomass ($134.30 gm^{-2}$) was observed in mulching with banana

leaves@ 12 t ha⁻¹. The results further indicated that the maximum weed control (77.84%) was explored in mulching with banana leaves@ 12 t ha⁻¹, followed by weed control (67.06%) was found in wheat straw mulch@12 t ha⁻¹. However, the no any weed control (%) was pointed out in control (weedy check) plot. Different mulching practices had major impact on sweet potato yield elements, and for weed control. The different mulch treatments, particularly black plastic (PL) and wheat straw (WS) mulches, have significantly reduced the fresh and dry weight of weeds.

Table 5: Effect of mulching practices on weed traits in cotton variety Sindh-1

Treatments	Weed traits			
	Weed density (m^{-2})	Weed fresh biomass (g m^{-2})	Weed dry biomass (g m^{-2})	Weed control (%)
Control (weedy check)	170.00 ^a	875.60 ^a	406.20 ^a	0.00 ^c
Mulching with banana leaves @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	55.67 ^c	293.80 ^c	134.30 ^c	77.84 ^a
Mulching with wheat straw @ 12 t ha ¹ (20 DAS)	64.33 ^b	330.36 ^b	150.53 ^b	67.06 ^b
SE	1.85	4.19	2.80	0.68
LSD@0.05	5.15	11.64	7.78	1.88

4. Discussion:

In all weed management activities over its weedy check, the amount of monopodial and sympodial divisions and matured bolls per plant, seed weight and seed cotton yield have also been improved (Nadeem et al., 2013). Mulching with banana leaves was found significantly better in increasing cotton yield than wheat straw and sunflower (Nawaz et al., 2013).

In order to increase seed cotton yield and cotton seed oil percentage, the seed index is a significant production component (Khan et al., 2010). Late picking increased the proportion of immature seeds; late sowing decreased crop maturity and fiber strength; and staple length mm was unaffected. (Soomro et al., 2004). Over the full range, the sensor readings were in line with actual measurements ($r^2 > 0.80$) (Sun et al., 2017).

Another research found that in totally non-mulched soil the incidence of weeds was greater than in mulched plots, because mulches have the potential to suffocate weeds based on their density (Essien et al., 2009). The main species of different weeds observed in the field included narrow leaf weeds (*Brachiaria reptans* L., *Cynodon dactylon* Pers., *Cyperus iria* L., *Desmostachya bipinnata* L., *Echinochloa colonum* L., and *Sorghum halepense* (L.) Pers.), broadleaf weeds (*Convolvulus arvensis* L., *Corchorus depressus* L., *Digera arvensis* Forssk., and *Trianthema portulacastrum* L.)

and Sedge grass (*Eleusine indica* L. Gaertn.). Our results are in conformism with that of Gul et al. (2009).

Black plastic mulch, accompanied by wheat straw mulch, demonstrated impressive weed control (Nwosisi et al., 2019).

5. Conclusion:

It is concluded that mulching with banana leaves (12 tons ha⁻¹) significantly increased agronomic and physiological traits of cotton variety Sindh-1 and reduced the weeds, as compared to mulching material of wheat straw @ 12 t. ha⁻¹ and control(untreated). Thus, it is suggested that mulching with banana leaves must be included in weed management plan of cotton in Pakistan.

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